

THE MECHANISM OF FORMING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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Annotation

Youth issues are closely related to education, morals, culture, health care, social relations, politics, law, religion, organization of free time, family, work, sports. Therefore, in scientific literature, these problems related to young people are studied both in the system of society and as a specific social group in a differential way. That is why there are cases of aggression, indifference, extremist moods and confusion among young people.

Keywords: Competence, youth, relations, politics, law, religion, social, professional, competence, sociology, social psychology, education, moods, aggression, culture.

The information society puts modern demands on us to increase the social activity of our youth. This, in turn, makes learning and mastering international standards of competitive personnel training and educating future specialists based on such principles becoming more urgent. "Today, the pan-European standard requires the wide use of interactive and communicative methods. Therefore, it has become one of the urgent issues to use the experience of advanced countries to bring the education at all stages of the education system of our country to the level of world standards, to create new generation textbooks based on continuous and integrated State education standards. For this reason, fundamental reform of the educational methodology at all stages of education and raising it to the international level is being carried out step by step in our country.

The multifunctional field of social education is based on the following principles:

- consistency - aimed at revealing the integrity of the object and the mechanisms that ensure it, determining the various relationships of a complex object and bringing them to a single example;
- integrity-reflects the internal unity of the object, its relative autonomy, independence from the environment;
- subjectivity - includes consideration from the point of view of the student's ability to set and adjust goals, be aware of motives, independently implement actions and assess compliance with the plan, draw up life plans;

- integration - ensures integration of irregular events, parts, elements into a whole (orderly and structural).

Issues related to youth are closely related to education, morals, culture, healthcare, social relations, politics, law, religion, organization of free time, family, work, sports. Therefore, in scientific literature, these problems related to young people are studied both in the system of society and as a specific social group in a differential way. That is why there are cases of aggression, indifference, extremist moods and confusion among young people. In order to prevent this, it is important to improve their knowledge and skills regarding the correct distribution of their free time, as well as the formation of their communicative competence and culture of communication. In this regard, people, "first of all, it is the most important task to form and educate the consciousness of young people on the basis of enlightenment. Of course, the implementation of reforms based on modern innovative ideas, developments and technologies in order to take a worthy place in the international arena is a priority aspect of our national development strategy.

The classification of three components and several parts, reflecting the important features of the educational system, is as follows:

a) includes the system of values, educational goals, educational principles, the vital content of the educational system, the methods of diagnosing and evaluating the results of this system, which are important for valuable subjects;

b) the spatial structure consisting of various forms and types of activities (individual, group, collective, frontal) is also developed by students in terms of self-organization and pedagogy;

c) coordination and pedagogical component, which is a set of pedagogical technologies of the educational process, the educational tasks of educational staff, the system of improving the professional competence of teachers, the system of pedagogical education and interaction with parents, education including managing the lim system.

Communicative competence of young people benefits in life classes, social relations and instability in society. Because social problems are eliminated on the basis of the enlightenment and communicative consciousness of the society and social sociability. It can be either productive for the society or a sign of limited, unstable, independence leading to the passivity of the individual. "The situation of principled equality of children of the same age arouses special interest in the adolescent in relation to this environment of relations, which

corresponds to the ethical content of the feeling of personal greatness that arises in the adolescent. Adolescents develop values that are more understandable and closer to their peers than adults. Communication with adults cannot replace communication with peers. For a teenager, communication with peers separates into the environment of his personal relationships, where he acts independently. He thinks that he has a right to it, he defends his rights, and that is why the inappropriate and rude intervention of adults leads to resentment and dissatisfaction. On the one hand, a teenager clearly shows a desire to communicate with peers and to engage in cooperative activities. The desire to live in a community, to have close friends, is a strong desire to be accepted, recognized, and respected by friends. This is becoming an important requirement. The most unpleasant situation for a teenager is the displeasure of the team and friends, unwillingness to communicate, and the most severe punishment is open or closed communication, not talking. Important norms of the friendship code of teenagers are respect for honor, equality, loyalty, help to a friend, correct speech. Acquiring the norms of friendship is an important achievement of a child in adolescence. According to psychologists, "during youth, there is a need to express oneself, to be communicative, to realize oneself, to choose the field of self-realization and its methods, first of all, in the youth will give". The ability of young people to control themselves, to analyze their life strategy, to study life perspectives is a necessity of life. This includes the following key indicators:

- problems that concern young people;
- feeling social;
- priority life values and plans;
- level of social maturity.

Assimilating the life experience of the older generation, teaching them the ways to benefit from work, and their training also have a positive effect on the communicative competence of teenagers. Social norms, values and wealth are the main socio-psychological managers and indicators of this process. It is these that determine the intellectual and practical activity of young people, the specifics of their problems, interests and expected results, self-management and management characteristics. At the same time, it shows the effectiveness of their social communication and the result of tolerant relations. "School and study occupy a large place in the life of a teenager. But despite the fact that they understand the importance and necessity of reading, different children look at this issue differently. For many, the fun of school is enhanced by the opportunity

to interact with peers, but the learning itself is greatly affected by this. A lesson for a teenager is not only a 45-minute study, but also a situation of communication with classmates and a teacher, enriched with many important actions, grades, and experiences. With the transition to secondary school, the study of teenagers becomes significantly more complicated: instead of one teacher, there are five or six new ones, their way of explaining and asking, as well as their demands and attitude towards students different. In addition, teachers do not know them well at first, and as a result, there are "favorite" and "unfavorite" teachers. Adolescents are knowledgeable and demanding, but fair, open-minded and civilized, who can explain the material in an interesting and clear way, who can organize the lesson in a uniform manner, who can engage in it, and who can make the lesson maximally productive for each student. they like teachers. In middle grades, students begin to learn and master the basics of science. Children will have to acquire a large amount of knowledge. By the end of adolescence, they begin to think about their future profession and, in general, their future."

So, on the basis of such an approach, building communicative competence in them, developing sociability, forming a culture of communication and tolerance in relations will benefit them in their future professional activities and social relations.

In conclusion, in today's globalized world, the communicative competence of teenagers directly depends on their worldview, way of thinking and, in general, their state of mind. The unstable and conflicting nature of the minds of young people definitely affects their behavior and activities, their sociability and social relations. First of all, nowadays the process of socialization of teenagers has become much more complicated, therefore the factors of their social maturity have changed a lot. These factors are characterized not only by the fact that teenagers work independently, but also by completing their education, having a profession, and becoming financially independent from adults. Second, there are factors that influence adolescent growth and adulthood. Each of these social mechanisms performs different tasks and has a different effect on the education of young people.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. New Uzbekistan strategy. -Tashkent.: Uzbekistan. 2021. -B. 303.
2. Kayumov O'. Socialization processes of the youth of Uzbekistan in the conditions of the formation of civil society. -Tashkent: Social Thought JFO'M, 2011.- B. 68-69.

- 3.<http://elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/item/12519-2021-06-02-11-23-40>
(Ўсмирларнинг психологик хусусиятлари)
- 4.Evatov, S. S. (2020). Modern social and pedagogical measures for the development of social competence among students. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(7), 484-489.
- 5.Evatov, S. S. (2021). Formation of students communicative competence in the process of continuous education. *Current research journal of pedagogics*, 2(05), 13-19.
- 6.Sobirovich, E. S. (2021). Developing Communicative Competence of Students: Historical and Pedagogical Experience. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(5), 108-111.
- 7.Sobirovich, E. S. (2021). Innovation experience in the development of communicative competence of students. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(05), 483-487.
- 8.Sobirovich, E. S. (2022). Content and scientific-pedagogical basis of the concept of communicative competence Teacher at Fergana State University. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 9, 176-180.
- 9.Sobirovich, E. S. (2022). On The Basis of Family and School Cooperation Theoretical and Methodological Fundamentals of Developing Communicative Competence of Adolescent Students. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 2(4), 73-77.
10. Abdulazizova, N., & Evatov, S. (2014). Factors preventing harmful habits in vocational college students. *Vestnik karakalpakskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta imeni berdaha*, 25(4), 38-41.
- 11.Эватов, С. С. (2016). The role of family in society and child's education in family. *Учёный XXI века*, (5-1 (18)), 46-49.
12. Evatov, S. S. (2022). Pedagogical conditions for the development of communicative competence of adolescent students on the basis of family and school cooperation. *Science and innovation*, 1(B3), 182-190.
13. Evatov, S. S., & Ibragimova, S. I. (2022). Pedagogical content of development of communicative competence of adolescent students. *Education and innovative research*, 8-9.
14. Evatov, S. S., & Nabieva, A. (2022). Reforms in improving the creativity and competence of young students. *Education and innovative research*, 10-11.